

MECHANICAL RECYCLING OF PRE-CONSUMER POLYETHYLENE TEREPHTHALATE (PET) WASTE

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Abstract: *The exponential rise in plastic waste, particularly polyesters such as polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polylactic acid (PLA) and other packaging materials, has become a pressing environmental concern on a global scale. To tackle this issue, mechanical recycling has emerged as a promising solution. Mechanical recycling of PET, such as any other polymer, involves a series of crucial steps, including collection, sorting, cleaning, size reduction, and reprocessing. These steps aim to convert polymer waste into high-quality recycled materials suitable for diverse applications, however they come with challenges that need to be addressed, the most significant risks are represented by contamination and degradation. The main advantages of the are reduced energy consumption, carbon emissions compared to the production of virgin PET and conservation of valuable resources by decreasing the demand for raw materials. In the paper prospect of pre-consumer recycled PET (rPET) for mechanical recycling is studied by evaluating the influence of multiple cycles of mechanical recycling on the thermal and mechanical properties. The results show that rPET can be mechanically recycled up to 7 times starting from regrind material, before losing its processability. However, the properties after 7 cycles of mechanical recycling are still acceptable for less demanding applications, since PET retain moduli quite well, strength on the other hand decreases more noticeable. Thermal properties do not change significantly, only small decreases in degradation temperatures were recorded and crystallization behaviour shifted to higher temperature.*

Keywords: mechanical recycling, regrind materials, pre-consumer waste, polyethylene terephthalate, reuse

1 INTRODUCTION

There is no need to emphasize that the exponential growth of plastic waste has become one of the most critical environmental challenges of our time. Among various plastic materials, polyethylene terephthalate (PET) stands out due to its widespread use in packaging applications, especially in the food and beverage industry (Hopewell, Dvorak and Kosior, 2009; Association of Plastic Manufacturers (Organization), 2020). To combat the environmental repercussions of PET waste, mechanical recycling has emerged as a promising and sustainable solution. Mechanical recycling involves the collection, sorting, cleaning, size reduction, and reprocessing of post-consumer and pre-consumer pet waste, transforming it into high-quality recycled materials suitable for a wide range of applications. By diverting PET waste from landfills and incineration, mechanical recycling significantly reduces the burden on the environment and conserves valuable resources (Volfand, 2019; Schyns and Shaver, 2021; Benyathiar *et al.*, 2022).

Mechanical recycling offers a promising solution to address the challenges of PET waste. By incorporating circular economy principles, recycling aims to close the loop in the life cycle of PET products. The process starts with the collection of PET waste, including both post-consumer and pre-consumer sources. Pre-consumer PET waste, also known as industrial or manufacturing waste, originates production of PET-based products and is usually not contaminated. Recycling pre-consumer waste presents an opportunity to intercept plastic waste before it reaches the consumer. Despite its potential, mechanical recycling faces certain challenges, particularly when dealing with post-consumer PET waste. Contamination from additives, processing residues, and incompatible polymers can affect the quality and purity of recycled pet materials. Additionally, mechanical recycling processes may induce thermal and mechanical degradation in the polymer, leading to a decline in performance attributes of the recycled PET. However, by avoiding main challenges of contamination and difficulties with separation of gathered waste the effectiveness of pre-consumer waste recycling is very prospective (Hopewell, Dvorak and Kosior, 2009; Volfand, 2019; Schyns and Shaver, 2021; Benyathiar *et al.*, 2022).

This study focuses on evaluating the prospects of utilizing pre-consumer PET for mechanical recycling. The study aims to assess the influence of multiple recycling cycles its thermal and mechanical properties. Understanding the possibilities of mechanical recycling for pre-consumer PET waste is crucial for promotion of such praxis in the industry and decrease in significant share of waste.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2. 1 Sample preparation

Ground PET pre-consumer bottles were supplied by Stramex PET d.o.o. (Podplat, SLO). The ground material consisted of various particle shapes and sizes ranging from fine dust to 3 mm in diameter, with the average shifted towards the upper limit.

The ground PET was dried in the Memmert 100-800 hot-air drying oven until the moisture content, determined with the Mettler Toledo HX204 moisture analyser, was below 0.025 % before injection moulding (Arburg Allrounder 320 C 500-100 Golden Edition with a screw diameter of 20 mm) into test specimens with the shape according to the standards ISO 527 (type 1BA), ISO 178 and ISO 179. The temperature profile was set to decrease from 290°C on the die to 270°C at the hopper, the screw rotated at 100 rpm⁻¹ at a backpressure of 30 bar, the injection speed was 50 mm/s, the holding pressure was set to 320 bar for 5 s, and the cooling was set to 25°C for 20 s. Last forty samples from each series were analysed for their properties, while the rest were milled using the Wanner C13.20 s mill for thermoplastics, and re-injected. Mechanical recycling, consisting of milling and injection moulding, was repeated until PET retained the processability which was 7 cycles since at the beginning of 8th cycle melt was already to degraded for it to be plasticized for injection.

2. 2 Characterization

The thermal and mechanical properties of the specimens were evaluated after each processing cycle. For thermal properties, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) were performed. Samples for DSC (DSC 2, Mettler Toledo) weighing between 5 mg and 10 mg were prepared in aluminium crucibles. The temperature regime of the analysis consisted of a 5 min isothermal section at 0°C followed by heating from 0°C to 280°C at 10°C/min, at 280°C there was a 5 min isothermal section followed by cooling at 10°C/min, in two cycles, and the entire measurement was performed in nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 20 mL/min. TGA analyses were performed using a Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC 3+. Samples of approximately 10 mg prepared in an alumina crucible were heated from 40°C to 600°C in a nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 20 mL/min, followed by heating from 600°C to 700°C at 10°C/min in an oxygen atmosphere (20 mL/min). Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was performed using a Perkin Elmer DMA 8000 dynamic mechanical analyser in dual cantilever mode. Samples were heated at 2°C/min from room temperature to

170°C in an air atmosphere and dynamically loaded at a frequency of 1 Hz and an amplitude of 20 μm .

Mechanical evaluation included tensile, flexural, and impact tests on notched specimens using the Charpy method. Tensile and flexural properties were determined using the Shimadzu AG-X plus universal testing machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell and an optical strain gauge. The tensile test was performed according to ISO 527-1 and the flexural test according to ISO 178. Impact strength was tested according to ISO 179 standard using Dongguan Liyi LY-JJD5 impact strength tester. Notched specimens were tested using a 1 J pendulum. The results of tensile and flexural tests represent the average of 5 specimen measurements each, while 10 specimens were submitted to impact toughness testing.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The thermal behaviour of rPET during multiple processing cycles was investigated using DSC, results of second heating are presented in Table 1. Throughout the processing cycles, the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the rPET remained relatively stable, with only minor fluctuations observed. The observed T_g values ranged from approximately 75.43°C to 80.76°C. On the other hand, melting points (T_m) and enthalpies of melting are indicating slightly increasing trends, corresponding to eased crystallization of PET subjected to more processing cycles due to shortening of polymer chains.

Table 5. DSC results of second heating of injection moulded samples.

Processing cycle	T_g (°C)	C_p (J/gK)	T_{m1} (°C)	T_{m2} (°C)	ΔH_m (J/g)
1	80.76	0.075	241.58	248.16	34.98
2	80.01	0.065	241.57	247.74	35.20
3	80.62	0.030	243.80	248.01	37.27
4	75.43	0.026	244.53	249.50	39.37
5	79.81	0.043	244.80	249.50	41.57
6	79.67	0.029	245.28	249.99	41.51
7	79.75	0.030	246.37	250.44	41.84

For insight in thermal stability TGA was employed. Degradation temperatures in dependence of processing cycles are presented in Figure 1. The most noticeable drop in degradation temperature was recorded from 2nd to 3rd reprocessing, but was still less than 5°C. Following reprocessing did not affect thermal stability in sense of degradation temperature since no further drop was recorded.

Figure 6. Degradation temperatures of samples determined by TGA.

Figure 2 presents determined tensile modulus in dependence of processing cycle. Significant decrease was recorded from 1st to 2nd reprocessing while further reprocessing did not affect it significantly since all the values remained in range of standard deviations indicating that material do not suffer significant decreases in stiffness due to multiple mechanical recycling.

Figure 2. Tensile modulus in dependence of processing cycles.

Flexural modulus was also evaluated, results are presented in Figure 3. Results are indicating slightly increasing trend in flexural stiffness with more processing cycles presumably due to recorded increase in crystalline domains due to chain shortening and corresponding enabling more compact packing of polymer chains.

Figure 3. Flexural modulus in dependence of processing cycles.

Tensile strength initially does not seem to be negatively affected by reprocessing, as can be seen in Figure 4. Significant decrease was recorded from 5th cycle onwards. This trend points to complex microstructure behaviour of rPET during reprocessing, while also indicating the material's potential for multiple cycles of mechanical recycling.

Figure 4. Tensile strength in dependence of processing cycles.

Figure 5 presents graphical representation of the determined flexural strengths. The results exhibit the same trend, as was observed with tensile strengths, reinforcing the significance of observed trend and suggests that pre-consumer rPET can be mechanically recycled at least up to five times while still retaining good mechanical performance.

Figure 5. Flexural strength in dependence of processing cycles.

The storage modulus, determined by DMA offers further insight into material's behaviour. Figure 6 presents the determined storage modulus of samples at 30°C. The storage modulus values show significant decrease with each reprocessing up to 5th cycle, where trend reverses and storage modulus gradually returns to initial values. The initial decrease is indicating enhanced molecular mobility due to chain scission, while the subsequent increases could be explained by chain scission reaching a point where chains are able to pack themselves more efficiently.

Figure 6. Storage modulus at 30°C determined by DMA.

Figure 7 presents the loss factors values determined with DMA at its peak. The trend exhibits a decrease with more processing cycles indicating a reduction in

the material's damping ability and stiffer response with its subsection to more reprocessing. The values remain comparable up to 3rd reprocessing, after which the most significant decrease occurs followed by steady declines in each subsequent cycle.

Figure 7. Loss factor determined by DMA.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the rising issue of plastic waste, particularly polyesters such as PET, necessitates the adoption of effective recycling strategies. Mechanical recycling has emerged as a promising solution, offering reduced energy consumption, lower carbon emissions, and the conservation of valuable resources compared to the production of virgin PET. This article has focused on the prospects of utilizing pre-consumer PET for mechanical recycling, specifically evaluating its thermal and mechanical properties after multiple recycling cycles.

The observed trends reveal the dynamic nature of rPET's response to reprocessing and highlighting its potential for mechanical recycling. The study findings indicate that rPET can undergo mechanical recycling up to seven times starting from virgin material before experiencing a loss in processability. Furthermore, suggests that while initial cycles of reprocessing do not significantly impact tensile strength, flexural strength, and storage modulus, a clear trend of decline emerges after a certain point, usually between 4th and 5th reprocessing, where appears to be a critical threshold, beyond which a more noticeable changes of material behaviour occur which is attributed to enhanced molecular mobility, chain scission, and potential microstructural changes induced by the recycling process.

Moving forward, further research and innovation are needed to address the challenges of contamination and degradation in mechanical recycling processes since potential of mechanical recycling of uncontaminated material's is clear. Hopefully, these results will encourage more mechanical recycling of pre-consumer waste.

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